

An Expert Evaluation of a VR Intervention for Children with ASD

Yujing Zhang, Conor Keighrey, Niall Murray

Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest

Abstract

The potential of technology-based interventions for children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) has received significant attention in recent years. In particular, immersive and interactive technologies such as virtual reality (VR) are being compared with traditional approaches. VR interventions claim to bring a richer experience to children with ASD. However, with it comes the potential risk of more sensory stimulation. The existing evaluations are focused on user evaluation, and then there is a gap in the expert evaluation of the autism intervention system to appropriately inform the design of such interventions. In this paper, the author proposes an expert evaluation-based method to conduct a comprehensive test of autism intervention systems.

Keywords: ASD, Children, Intervention, Expert Evaluation, VR.

1 Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a complex developmental disorder. Individuals with ASD may be known to display limited facial expressions, atypical attention patterns, and delayed communication and cognitive abilities [Hyman et al., 2020]. Especially, children with ASD are reported to have challenges in social situations compared to typically developing (TD) peers [Broekhof et al., 2015]. These symptoms in individuals with ASD are associated with impaired theory of mind (ToM) [Astington and Jenkins, 1995], which makes people affected usually experience difficulty in understanding and interpreting the feelings and desires of others. Intervention can help to develop strategies for ToM in children with ASD in the early stage [Tager-Flusberg, 2007] and acquire basic social skills. Therefore, interventions targeting children are important. The combination of virtual reality (VR) technologies with traditional interventions in recent years has given rise to multimedia interventions. Meanwhile, the evaluation of VR intervention requires more attention.

Currently, the autism intervention systems are tested by people with ASD. The research on the evaluation of interventions for adults with ASD includes recording and analysing subjective, objective, and physiological data [Adjorlu et al., 2019, Zhang et al., 2017]. There are fewer studies on interventions for children with ASD, where accurate feedback cannot be provided due to difficulty with language comprehension in children with ASD [Kjellmer et al., 2012]. These assessments are therefore either subjective by parents and therapists [Miller et al., 2020], or objectively through their performance data as required by the intervention [Scattone, 2008, Uzuegbunam et al., 2017].

Children with ASD may be overreactive to sensory input and special environments [Corbett et al., 2009]. So, there are many potential challenges to evaluating multimedia-based interventions with them. Also, due to the fact that the user group is children with ASD, they provide very limited subjective feedback in terms of system measurement. There is a lack of comprehensive and professional evaluation of the intervention for children with

Figure 1: Usability evaluation method.

ASD, even though the systems are designed based on therapist advice [Scattone, 2008, Miller et al., 2020] or heuristic evaluation principles [Moreno et al., 2020]. The usability evaluation can be done in two methods, user evaluation and expert evaluation [Nielsen, 1994, Molich and Dumas, 2008], as shown in Figure 1. The former is primarily a test for target users, while the latter is a test of the system by a small number of experts in a particular field.

The expert evaluation method has been used to measure VR applications [Kloster and Babic, 2019, Kangas et al., 2022, Sutcliffe and Gault, 2004]. Experts can imagine the problems that users may encounter, also, they can identify problems in the system that users may not notice [Molich and Dumas, 2008]. Compared with evaluating the intervention system by testing children with ASD, the expert evaluation will be more detailed and comprehensive to help to design the system more accurately. Moreover, they can identify potential threats in the system and keep the children out of harm's way.

Hence, this paper presents an expert evaluation method to measure the VR intervention for children with ASD. Different from previous studies, it brings a new perspective to testing and evaluating the system. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows, Section 2 introduces existing VR evaluation, and Section 3 presents the design of the expert evaluation.

2 Related Work

This section introduces related works to this research.

2.1 The Usability of User Evaluation for VR Interventions

Current VR intervention studies focus on testing with targeting users. Interventions for adults and adolescents can be tested and evaluated by users, but the interventions for children are tested on children and evaluated by non-users (their parents/therapists).

2.1.1 User Testing and Non-Users Evaluation

A VR training evaluation was presented by [Miller et al., 2020]. It focused on teaching children with ASD to gain air travel skills and measure their experience through parents' feedback and clinic observations. Five children (aged 4-8 years old) attended and used iPhone X with a Google Cardboard device to experience the VR intervention. Their parents quantified their travel skills on a 5-Likert Scale air travel questionnaire by pre-and post-intervention. A 4-Point clinical activity checkpoint (check-in, security, waiting at the gate, and boarding) was used during the intervention. A speech-language pathologist captured the clinical observations after each session and completed the responses to clinical communication observations. The results of the parents' questionnaires and clinical observations showed that the children's air travel skills improved after the intervention. The advantage of parental feedback is that they know their children very well, but their feedback is more subjective and focuses on their children's performance and lacks professional evaluation of the system.

A communication screen-based intervention [Scattone, 2008] collected the objective data of a nine-year-old boy through audio and video recorders, including eye contact, smile, and initiation as they occurred during the experiment. The experiment consisted of a baseline recording, a video story intervention, and 5 minutes of social interactions. The boy repeated the intervention 1-2 times per week. After three months, the boy's eye contact improved, but the other two targeted skills did not significantly increase. The study showed the video story has the potential possible to help children with ASD to improve their conversation skills. Another study [Uzuegbunam et al., 2017] invited three children (aged 7-11 years old) to practice social etiquette skills based on a computer screen. It recorded the users' body movements data, greeting responses time, frequency of greetings, and eye gaze data. Also, this experiment contained three phases, baseline, intervention, and maintenance. The children had the intervention for 6-14 days and then their maintenance results showed that only one child improved in all targeted skills, and the other two only improved in eye contact. The above studies can be summarised that the evaluation of children's performance takes longer because it requires documentation of baseline, intervention, and maintenance

for data comparison. At the same time, it increases the risk of children being exposed to experiments.

2.1.2 User Testing and Evaluation

A head-mounted display (HMD)-based VR music intervention [Adjorlu et al., 2019] to reduce social anxiety in adolescents with ASD, collected their subjective feedback through pre-and post-questionnaires. Three male participants (aged 18-20 years old) completed the experiment. They were asked to finish the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSA) questionnaire with 5 Smiley-Likert Scale for measuring their anxiety level and frequency before the experiment. After the VR intervention, to explore the participants' immersive experience, they were asked to answer four questions from the Witmer Singer Presence Questionnaire (PQ) and four questions from the Immersive Tendency Questionnaire (ITQ), all using 7 Smiley-Likert Scale. One participant failed because he could not understand the questions, and the rest of them reported their feedback through the questionnaires. From this it can be seen that the data of the questionnaire (user subjective data) may be unreliable, the questionnaire requires users to have language comprehension skills, but users with ASD may not understand the questions fully.

Another HMD-based VR driving intervention [Zhang et al., 2017] was designed to improve the driving skills of adolescents with ASD and measure cognitive load through driving performance, questionnaires, and physiological signals. During the experiment, twenty participants (aged 13-18 years old) were asked to complete the questionnaires to rate their affective and cognitive states. Meanwhile, various sensors collected the data, including electrocardiogram (ECG), electromyography (EMG), respiration (RSP), skin temperature (SKT), photoplethysmography (PPG), and galvanic skin response (GSR). The performance data included the brake accelerator, failure times, and driving score. Comparing the different types of data, the results showed that multimodal fusion schemes could provide a more accurate measure of users' cognitive load. The design of the questionnaire plays a vital role, which determines the quality of the evaluation, but using subjective data and physiological signals to measure users' experiences can enhance evaluation accuracy.

2.2 The Usability of Expert Evaluation for VR Systems

A Mobile VR application [Kloster and Babic, 2019] for neck exercise was evaluated by one physiotherapist through an open-ended interview. He positively evaluated the prototype and gave advice that could make the neck exercises more entertaining. Because according to his work experience, the patients are sometimes not self-motivated enough to maintain the efficiency of their treatment. Also, six users participated in the test, but they only reported feedback on the 5-Likert Scale, with no more subjective feedback compared to expert feedback. The advantage of expert evaluation is experts can provide clear professional advice for the system based on their experience.

An HMD-based VR medical landmarking system [Kangas et al., 2022] for identifying and marking cephalometric landmarks was evaluated by a group of medical experts. The system can be used in three different conditions: "VR+Controller", "VR+Pen", and "Mouse+Display". Four medical experts participated in the experiment, and each completed the three condition tests. The evaluation method included objective measures (task completion times and marking accuracy) and subjective questions (evaluation of each interaction method and ranking of all interaction methods). The objective results showed the "VR+Pen" cost more time but had better marking accuracy than other conditions. In the subjective feedback, "VR+Controller" had the highest praise, and "VR+Pen" was the last, but it was rated as having the most potential for development by experts. The other advantage of the expert evaluation is that the experts with a small number can finish the comparison study.

Therefore, considering the advantages of expert evaluation (discussed above), the VR intervention for children with ASD can be tested and evaluated by experts, especially in pilot tests. It not only solves the problem of limited feedback for children with ASD but eliminates the risks of experimentation on them. Based on the related works, the evaluation can be included implicit and explicit measurements to improve the evaluation accuracy. The author proposes an expert evaluation design, including subjective questionnaires, objective measures, and physiological monitoring in Section 3.

3 Proposed Expert Evaluation Design

The author proposed the expert evaluation design, this section consists of a system introduction, participant screening, and various measurements.

3.1 VR Intervention System Set Up

The VR intervention application in this research is based on the Social Story™ book designed to improve social skills in children with ASD through experiencing immersive video stories [Zhang et al., 2023]. The application was developed in Unity Version 2021.3.6f1 and can be used in two conditions, screen-based and HMD-based, as shown in Table 1. Participants need to wear sensors to experience the intervention in two conditions and finish the post-experience questionnaires. The whole process is around 10 minutes, including 5 minutes of baseline recording, 2 minutes of intervention, and 3 minutes of completing questionnaires.

Condition	Experience	Device
Screen-based	2D Story	24-inch computer screen
VR-based	Immersive 3D Story	HTC-Vive Pro Eye

Table 1: The VR intervention application in two conditions.

3.2 Participants

According to ITU-T P.910's instructions on the number of experts required [P.910, 2022], the author plans to invite four experts working in the field of ASD. At the same time, it is necessary to avoid the homogeneity of the usability evaluator structure, resulting in insufficient evaluation objectively [Rosenbaum, 1989]. Considered bringing together experts in different areas of ASD in the proposed plan, including a clinical psychologist, a behavioural psychologist, a behaviour analyst, and a speech and language pathologist. The experts will complete the two conditions experiments. The process aims to gain feedback from them on the application design and evaluate the 2D and immersive 3D experience.

3.3 Subjective Questionnaires

The subjective questionnaires have consisted of three different types of questionnaires.

3.3.1 7-Likert Scale Questions

The 8 questions are selected from the 24-question Film Immersive Experience Questionnaire [Rigby et al., 2019] based on the VR story intervention content, as shown in Table 2. The questionnaire is consisted of three factors: immersion (Q1, Q3, Q6), enjoyment (Q2, Q5, Q8), and comprehension (Q4, Q7). The 8 questions need to be filled after each experiment by experts, and the 7-Likert Scales aim to get the quantitative data from them.

Q1	To what extent did the video hold your attention?
Q2	To what extent did you enjoy the imagery?
Q3	To what extent did you notice events taking place around you?
Q4	To what extent did you find the concepts and themes easy to understand?
Q5	To what extent did you feel motivated to keep on watching?
Q6	To what extent did you feel you were focused on the video?
Q7	How well do you think you understood what happened?
Q8	Would you like to watch more of this, or similar content, in the future?

Table 2: The questions with 7-Likert Scales to evaluate the experience.

3.3.2 Comparison Questions

The 3 questions shown in Table 3 are modified based on Kangas’s questionnaire [Kangas et al., 2022], which aims to evaluate the screen-based and HMD-based and explore which experience is more acceptable for children with ASD. The experts need to complete this comparison questionnaire by combing the VR story intervention experience and imagining the needs of children with ASD to provide the indicative data.

Q1	Which experience do you think the children with ASD would enjoy most?
Q2	Which experience would be more appropriate for children with ASD?
Q3	Which experience has more potential for development?

Table 3: The questions to compare the two different experiences.

3.3.3 Open-ended Questions

The open-ended questions as shown in Table 4 are served for upgrading the application through experts’ advice. Also, experts need to explore the potential risk of the application and provide solutions.

Q1	Where does the story content need to be improved?
Q2	How about this scene (background music, light, colour, voice, time, character)?
Q3	What are the potential risks for children with ASD in this application and how to avoid them?
Q4	Which age group of children with ASD is this application suitable for?

Table 4: The Open-ended questions based on the application.

3.4 Objective Measures

In objective measures, the screen-based application and HMD-based application are different, as shown in Figure 2. The user interface of screen-based intervention is 2D and fixed by moving four virtual cameras. The HMD-based intervention depends on the user’s head movement, users will freely look around in the immersive environment. Unity Recorder is designed to record the user’s entire usage process as mp4 files. Microsoft Azure Kinect DK records the body movements and gestures, which captures depth and colour images at a frame rate of 30 fps.

Figure 2: The objective measures recording of screen-based and HMD-based.

3.5 Physiological Monitoring

According to the ITU-T P.1320 standard, in addition to subjective questionnaires and objective measures, physiological signals are also important in the system evaluation [P.1320, 2022]. It is associated with covert processes that may cause emotional arousal. The heart rate (HR) and electrodermal activity (EDA) can reflect people’s real inner activities, including stress levels and emotional reactions [Trotman et al., 2019, Prokasy, 2012,

Bradley et al., 2001]. Eye data measurement consists of gaze tracking, eye blinking, and pupillometry for measuring fatigue, cybersickness, and attention [Stern et al., 1994, Lopes et al., 2020]. Moreover, the head movement data should be recorded due to the head movement triggers the eye muscles [Somisetty et al., 2019]. The HR and EDA data will be monitored by the E4 wristband, and the eyes and head data will be recorded by HTC Vive Pro Eye and Tobii Pro Spark under two conditions separately, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The various sensors in physiological monitoring.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper introduces the design of an expert evaluation method to measure VR intervention for children with ASD. The aim is to obtain more professional and comprehensive feedback. The author summarised the existing intervention evaluations and find out a gap in the evaluation of VR intervention for children with ASD, and then proposed that the expert evaluation method could be used to fill this gap. Based on the content of the VR intervention system, the author designed the evaluation includes post-experience questionnaires, objective measures, and physiological monitoring. The author plans to test the expert evaluation method on the VR intervention in future work.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by the President's Doctoral Scholarship of the Technological University of the Shannon.

References

- [Adjorlu et al., 2019] Adjorlu, A., Barriga, N. B. B., and Serafin, S. (2019). Virtual reality music intervention to reduce social anxiety in adolescents diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder. In *16th Sound and music computing conference*, pages 261–268. Sound and Music Computing Network.
- [Astington and Jenkins, 1995] Astington, J. W. and Jenkins, J. M. (1995). Theory of mind development and social understanding. *Cognition & Emotion*, 9(2-3):151–165.
- [Bradley et al., 2001] Bradley, M. M., Codispoti, M., Cuthbert, B. N., and Lang, P. J. (2001). Emotion and motivation I: defensive and appetitive reactions in picture processing. *Emotion*, 1(3):276.
- [Broekhof et al., 2015] Broekhof, E., Ketelaar, L., Stockmann, L., van Zijp, A., Bos, M. G., and Rieffe, C. (2015). The understanding of intentions, desires and beliefs in young children with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal*

of autism and developmental disorders, 45:2035–2045.

- [Corbett et al., 2009] Corbett, B. A., Schupp, C. W., Levine, S., and Mendoza, S. (2009). Comparing cortisol, stress, and sensory sensitivity in children with autism. *Autism Research*, 2(1):39–49.
- [Hyman et al., 2020] Hyman, S. L., Levy, S. E., Myers, S. M., Kuo, D. Z., Apkon, S., Davidson, L. F., Eller-Beck, K. A., Foster, J. E., Noritz, G. H., Leppert, M. O., et al. (2020). Identification, evaluation, and management of children with autism spectrum disorder. *Pediatrics*, 145(1).
- [Kangas et al., 2022] Kangas, J., Li, Z., and Raisamo, R. (2022). Expert evaluation of haptic virtual reality user interfaces for medical landmarking. In *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems Extended Abstracts*, pages 1–7.
- [Kjellmer et al., 2012] Kjellmer, L., Hedvall, Å., Holm, A., Fernell, E., Gillberg, C., and Norrelgen, F. (2012). Language comprehension in preschoolers with autism spectrum disorders without intellectual disability: Use of the Reynell developmental language scales. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 6(3):1119–1125.
- [Kloster and Babic, 2019] Kloster, M. and Babic, A. (2019). Mobile VR application for neck exercises. In *ICIMTH*, pages 206–209.
- [Lopes et al., 2020] Lopes, P., Tian, N., and Boulic, R. (2020). Exploring blink-rate behaviors for cybersickness detection in VR. In *2020 IEEE conference on virtual reality and 3D user interfaces abstracts and workshops (VRW)*, pages 794–795. IEEE.
- [Miller et al., 2020] Miller, I. T., Wiederhold, B. K., Miller, C. S., and Wiederhold, M. D. (2020). Virtual reality air travel training with children on the autism spectrum: A preliminary report. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 23(1):10–15.
- [Molich and Dumas, 2008] Molich, R. and Dumas, J. S. (2008). *Comparative usability evaluation (cue-4)*. Behaviour & Information Technology, 27(3):263–281.
- [Moreno et al., 2020] Moreno, G., Moreira, F., Collazos, C. A., and Fardoun, H. M. (2020). Recommendations for the design of inclusive apps for the treatment of autism: An approach to design focused on inclusive users. In *2020 15th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI)*, pages 1–6. IEEE.
- [Nielsen, 1994] Nielsen, J. (1994). Heuristic evaluation. *Usability Inspection Methods*.
- [P.1320, 2022] P.1320, I.-T. (2022). P.1320: Quality of experience assessment of extended reality meetings. The last version was published in 07/22.
- [P.910, 2022] P.910, I.-T. (2022). P.910: Subjective video quality assessment methods for multimedia applications. The last version was published in 07/22.
- [Prokasy, 2012] Prokasy, W. (2012). Electrodermal activity in psychological research. *Elsevier*.
- [Rigby et al., 2019] Rigby, J. M., Brumby, D. P., Gould, S. J., and Cox, A. L. (2019). Development of a questionnaire to measure immersion in video media: The film IEQ. In *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM International Conference on Interactive Experiences for TV and Online Video*, pages 35–46.
- [Rosenbaum, 1989] Rosenbaum, S. (1989). Usability evaluations versus usability testing: When and why? *IEEE transactions on professional communication*, 32(4):210–216
- [Scattone, 2008] Scattone, D. (2008). Enhancing the conversation skills of a boy with Asperger’s disorder through social stories™ and video modeling. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 38:395–400.
- [Somisetty et al., 2019] Somisetty, S. et al. (2019). Neuroanatomy, vestibuloocular reflex.
- [Stern et al., 1994] Stern, J. A., Boyer, D., and Schroeder, D. (1994). Blink rate: a possible measure of fatigue. *Human factors*, 36(2):285–297.

- [Sutcliffe and Gault, 2004] Sutcliffe, A. and Gault, B. (2004). Heuristic evaluation of virtual reality applications. *Interacting with computers*, 16(4):831–849.
- [Tager-Flusberg, 2007] Tager-Flusberg, H. (2007). Evaluating the theory-of-mind hypothesis of autism. *Current Directions in psychological science*, 16(6):311–315.
- [Trotman et al., 2019] Trotman, G. P., Veldhuijzen van Zanten, J. J., Davies, J., Möller, C., Ginty, A. T., and Williams, S. E. (2019). Associations between heart rate, perceived heart rate, and anxiety during acute psychological stress. *Anxiety, Stress, & Coping*, 32(6):711–727.
- [Uzuegbunam et al., 2017] Uzuegbunam, N., Wong, W. H., Cheung, S.-C. S., and Ruble, L. (2017). Mebook: multimedia social greetings intervention for children with autism spectrum disorders. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 11(4):520–535.
- [Zhang et al., 2017] Zhang, L., Wade, J., Bian, D., Fan, J., Swanson, A., Weitlauf, A., Warren, Z., and Sarkar, N. (2017). Cognitive load measurement in a virtual reality-based driving system for autism intervention. *IEEE Transactions on affective computing*, 8(2):176–189.
- [Zhang et al., 2023] Zhang, Y., Keighrey, C., and Murray, N. (2023). A VR intervention based on social story™ to develop social skills in children with ASD. In *ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences*.